

Why is the entorhinal cortex a cradle of Alzheimer's disease?

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The entorhinal cortex (EC) is a critical hub for memory, navigation, and perception of time. The predominant early symptoms of Alzheimer's disease (AD) are memory loss and disorientation to time or place, and when these become clinically diagnosable, EC has already undergone substantial degeneration, making it a primary site for disease onset. Because effective therapy for AD will have to prevent this degeneration, the value of focusing on this part of the brain as an arena for testing competing etiological explanations and their associated therapeutic implications is still underappreciated. Current explanations of the early etiology of AD can be broadly divided into two groups, depending on whether the disease is thought to be triggered by infectious agents. Here, in the context of the physiology of EC, we address this dichotomy and argue that the integration of key elements from both sides may be necessary to explain pivotal experimental findings on the native and pathophysiological roles of A β and tau.

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Introduction

The early etiology of late-onset AD (hereafter referred to simply as AD) is likely tied to intraneuronal accumulation of amyloid- β (A β) oligomers (Kibro-Flatmoen et al., 2021) and neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs) formed from hyperphosphorylated tau proteins (p-tau) (Berron et al., 2021). Together, these two pathologies are involved in a process that eventually leads to massive synaptic and neuronal degeneration. Most attempts to explain this pathological development acknowledge that the emergence of senescent physiology during normal aging constitutes the primary facilitating environment for disease onset.

However, within the above explanatory setting, in terms of the mechanisms proposed to cause the early etiology of AD and the choice of experimental data used as supporting evidence, there exist a variety of different expositions. In general, these can be separated into two categories according to whether the abnormal generation of A β and p-tau is thought to arise from an immune response to an acute microbial or viral brain in-

fection that has become dysfunctional. This categorization is pertinent because the way we interpret experimental data and the possibilities that may exist for targeted early therapeutic intervention are likely very much dependent on the presence or absence of a neuron-specific immune response to brain infection established by natural selection.

Before the onset of clinical symptoms in AD, there is an accumulation of intracellular A β followed by p-tau, and this is particularly prominent in layer II neurons in the lateral domain of the EC, that is, close to the rhinal fissure (Kibro-Flatmoen et al., 2021; Berron et al., 2021). Numerous studies conclude that lateral ECLII neurons are generally among the first neurons to undergo degeneration as the disease progresses (Gómez-Isla et al., 1996; Kordower et al., 2001; Kulason et al., 2019; Holbrook et al., 2020). In line with this, an analysis of tau-positron emission tomography scans in a very large cohort uncovered four distinct but consistent spatiotemporal patterns of tau buildup in AD that were consistent with the idea that the EC was the point of origin (Vogel et al., 2021). This finding was substantiated in a recent study on another large cohort, in which EC was found to be the primary region for pathological tau seeding (Alexandersen et al., 2025). Since ECLII neurons are crucial for creating spatial and relational frameworks that support our memory system, this explains the prominence of memory impairment among early AD symptoms, linking the initial neurodegenerative events in AD to the loss of functionally defined neurons.

Here, in the context of the anatomy and molecular physiology of the EC, and guided by the general observation that an immune response in the elderly may be induced by agents very different from those it has evolved to respond to, we propose that major explanatory elements from both sides of the abovementioned dichotomy may need to be combined to reconcile pivotal experimental data. We further show that this provides fresh perspectives on why mitochondrial dysfunction is an integral part of the early AD phenotype and on how this dysfunction relates to the function of A β and p-tau under native physiological conditions.

Outline of relevant EC features

EC location and structure

The EC is located in the medial temporal lobe and serves as the major input and output structure of the hippocampal formation, forming the nodal point in cortico-hippocampal circuits (Witter et al., 2017). In addition, it performs unique computations that generate a spatial metric and a representation of order and duration (Sugar and Moser, 2019), computations that are likely foundational elements of declarative memory (van Strien et al., 2009).

The degree of cyto- and chemoarchitectural organization of human EC defines a gradient that runs from its anterolateral (highly organized) to its posteromedial side (less organized), and there is a clear correspondence between this gradient and how the EC connects to the hippocampus. Projections from the anterolateral extreme of the EC target the posterior extreme of the hippocampus, whereas projections from progressively more posteromedial regions of the EC increasingly target the anterior portion of the hippocampus (Kobro-Flatmoen and Witter, 2019). Because large neurons in the superficially located layer II (ECLII) along the lateral extremity of the EC are particularly prone to degeneration before the appearance of clinical AD symptoms (Berron et al., 2021; Kulason et al., 2019), we will focus primarily on these.

EC and brain infection

Olfactory receptor neurons have their dendrites in the epithelium of the nasal cavity and project their axons onto mitral cells (van Riel et al., 2015). Since the dendrites of lateral ECLII neurons receive direct projections from mitral cells in the olfactory bulb (Wouterlood and Nederlof, 1983), there are only two synapses between LECLII neurons and olfactory receptor neurons. At least 14 types of neurovirulent viruses can use the olfactory nerve as a shortcut to the central nervous system (CNS) (van Riel et al., 2015), and intranasal inoculation has been a commonly used method to induce viral brain infection in model animals for several decades (Stroop et al., 1990). Although the actual transport mechanisms and subsequent spread of viral infections through the CNS remain poorly understood (van Riel et al., 2015), available data clearly suggest that lateral ECLII neurons can be exposed to viral infection through their connection with olfactory receptor neurons and serve as a portal for further CNS infection.

Furthermore, the EC receives vascular input from the posterior and middle cerebral arteries, which forms particularly dense reticulated networks around individual clusters of ECLII neurons. Together with the neuronal clusters themselves, these networks give rise to characteristic bumps on the surface of the EC, known as the entorhinal verrucae (Simic et al., 2005). Due to this apparent redundancy in vascular input, ECLII has been suggested to be especially vulnerable to blood-borne

inflammatory factors (Stranahan and Mattson, 2010). This would imply that ECLII neurons may also be particularly exposed to bloodborne pathogens.

Link between reelin, A β , p-tau and AD development

The function of the large glycoprotein reelin in the adult brain includes synaptic modulation, enhancement of spine density, and promotion of long-term potentiation (Qiu et al., 2006). The protein has a particularly strong expression in a subset of interneurons scattered throughout the cortical layers and, notably, in principal neurons situated in the lateral domain of ECLII. In rodents, this means that these neurons reside in the part closest to the rhinal sulcus, while in humans they are closest to the collateral sulcus. A peculiar feature of this expression is that it is gradually less pronounced as one moves successively further away from the rhinal/collateral sulcus, that is, in the ventromedial direction (Kobro-Flatmoen and Witter, 2019). In what follows, we refer to the laterally situated strongly reelin-expressing ECLII neurons as Re⁺ECLII neurons.

Re⁺ECLII neurons have enormous dendritic trees that fan into layer I, where they span a 360° extent whose distal diameter reaches up to 900 μ m while carrying a high density of dendritic spines, reflecting a very large number of excitatory synapses (Canto and Witter, 2012). The imposing nature of these dendrites is further reflected by the fact that a single Re⁺ECLII neuron collects direct input from at least five separate cortical areas, in addition to multiple sources of subcortical modulatory input (Kobro-Flatmoen et al., 2021). Furthermore, these neurons give rise to particularly extensive axonal arborizations both in their downstream hippocampal target zones and locally within the EC (Tamamaki and Nijo, 1993).

Long before A β plaques appear, intracellular A β in non-plaque constellations accumulate in Re⁺ECLII neurons in elderly cognitively intact humans (Kobro-Flatmoen et al., 2023b) and in early stage AD-subjects (Gouras et al., 2000; Kobro-Flatmoen et al., 2016). This phenomenon is recapitulated in some transgenic rat models (Kobro-Flatmoen et al., 2016, 2023a). Recently, it was shown that A β 42 binds directly to reelin, forming reelin-A β 42 complexes (A β 42_{reelin}) in Re⁺ECLII neurons (Kobro-Flatmoen et al., 2023a), suggesting that reelin may function as a sink for A β 42. Reelin signaling potently inhibits Glycogen Synthase Kinase 3 β (GSK3 β) (Hiesberger et al., 1999), one of the main tau-phosphorylating kinases in the brain, by binding and endocytosing ApoE receptor 2 (ApoER2) that activates a signaling cascade that causes inhibition of GSK3 β kinase activity (Jembrek et al., 2013). Although the functional significance of this tripartite constellation is not fully understood, its evolutionary conservation indicates physiological relevance in native physiology.

We (AKF, SWO) recently showed that a very simple mathematical model can describe the dynamics between intracellular A β , reelin, and p-tau formation

through the GSK3 β pathway as a function of short-term pathogen exposure (Kobro-Flatmoen and Omholt, 2025). Since the study was premised on that this dynamics was based on the same regulatory architecture in cortical neurons expressing low levels of reelin and Re⁺ECLII neurons, it rested on the assumption that reelin is present in sufficient quantity to influence the GSK3 β pathway in the vast majority of cortical neurons. To confirm that this is likely to be the case, a quantitative analysis of brain image data collected from 3, 12 and 18-month-old wild type rats was conducted. The analysis showed that almost all of the approximately 172500 neurons analyzed, located in five different cortical regions, possessed a reelin signal that was clearly above the background signal (Kobro-Flatmoen and Omholt, 2025). We project that this result also applies to humans. The model was validated by showing that it could recapitulate the phenotypic effects associated with two genotypes on opposite sides of the AD risk spectrum, and by recapitulating experimental data obtained by lowering the level of reelin in Re⁺ECLII neurons in McGill-R-Thy1-APP rats (Kobro-Flatmoen et al., 2023a). The model predicts that if A β and p-tau are part of an intraneuronal immune response in native physiology, the maximum possible production rate of A β must be considerably higher in Re⁺ECLII neurons than in most other cortical neurons. Otherwise, due to the binding between reelin and A β , Re⁺ECLII neurons would not be able to invoke an immune response comparable to that of other neurons that do not produce high levels of reelin. Since Re⁺ECLII neurons are unlikely to sport a lower immune response capacity than other cortical neurons, these results suggest that in a senescent physiology, Re⁺ECLII neurons may be particularly vulnerable to AD development (Kobro-Flatmoen and Omholt, 2025).

This contention was very recently examined by a much more elaborate mathematical model (Kobro-Flatmoen et al., 2025) that included the reported links between A β , p-tau and the endosome-autophagosome-lysosome pathway (EALP) (Koh et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2022). The model was designed to capture the intraneuronal dynamics of A β ₄₂, p-tau and A β ₄₂^{reelin} in Re⁺ECLII neurons, and in cortical neurons expressing low reelin levels, over a 20-year period as a function of senescence-driven recurring inflammation events of variable duration. The link between A β and EALP is a crucial component of the model, as it recapitulates the observation that disruption of EALP function is an early and progressive characteristic of the pathophysiology of AD (Knopman et al., 2021). A β oligomers and β -C-terminal fragment (β -CTF), another cleavage product of the amyloid precursor protein (APP), appear capable of inhibiting the activity of the endolysosomal vacuolar (H⁺)-adenosine triphosphatase (v-ATPase) proton pump. This inhibition causes endolysosomal alkalization (Song et al., 2020), leading to a general decrease in endolysosomal degradative capacity and subsequent

accumulation of degradation-tagged cellular cargo (Koh et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2022; Im et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2023). Through this mechanism, the model predicts that the intracellular amount of A β ₄₂^{reelin} in Re⁺ECLII neurons can easily accumulate to occupy more than 50% of the soma volume, fully consistent with experimental data (D'Andrea et al., 2001, 2002). In contrast, the model predicts that there will be no marked accumulation of A β ₄₂^{reelin} in cortical neurons expressing low levels of reelin. Furthermore, the model shows that it is fully conceivable that the accumulation of A β ₄₂^{reelin} is causally related to the observation that high intracellular levels of aggregation-prone p-tau fragments and cell death appear much earlier in Re⁺ECLII neurons than in other cortical neurons. This is because reduced translocation of the F1 tau fragment across the lysosomal membrane appears to be a critical mechanism to promote the formation of tau oligomers on the surface of these organelles through the creation of the aggregation-prone fragments F2 and F3 by cathepsin L lysosomal protease (Wang et al., 2009; Boyarko and Hook, 2021). Since the accumulation of A β ₄₂^{reelin} in lysosomes with a low degradative capacity creates a very large total lysosomal surface, tau aggregates will be disposed to be associated with this surface and thus lead to enhanced production of aggregation-prone tau fragments. The predictions of the model further clearly support findings implying that accumulation of intraneuronal A β ₄₂ can lead to neuronal lysis (D'Andrea et al., 2001; Gouras et al., 2000; Lee et al., 2022).

Thus, taken together, the results of the two mathematical models indicate that one possible reason why EC is a cradle of AD is the extremely high intracellular accumulation of A β ₄₂^{reelin} in Re⁺ECLII neurons due to the dysfunction of an ancient immune response. However, it should be acknowledged that the models did not explicitly incorporate mitochondrial dysfunction, which is clearly of importance in the very early etiology of AD (Olajide et al., 2021).

Link between reelin, Bnip3, energy consumption in ECLII neurons and ROS load

High expression of the canonical promitophagic BCL2 interacting protein 3 (Bnip3) is a unique feature of Re⁺ECLII neurons (Omholt et al., 2024). This characteristic strongly indicates that these neurons have a particularly high mitochondrial turnover rate and therefore are likely to have an energy requirement much higher than that of most other cortical neurons (Khan et al., 2014). This is further supported by the facts that most brain energy is used for synaptic transmission (Harris et al., 2012), that mitochondria provide the lion's share of brain energy (Harris et al., 2012), and that the presence of high levels of reelin implicates frequent and energetically demanding remodeling of synaptic contacts (Omholt et al., 2024).

EC and mitochondrial dysfunction in AD

In vivo measurements using a positron emission tomography (PET) probe to assay levels of mitochondrial complex I (MC-I) showed a prominent oxidative metabolic failure in the medial temporal lobe of subjects with early-stage AD compared to controls (Terada et al., 2020). Neurons with a particularly high energy requirement are likely to be particularly sensitive to impaired mitochondrial function. Given the very high metabolic demand of Re⁺ECLII neurons, it follows that if these neurons suffer impaired mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS) function, they will quickly become dysfunctional. This is fully consistent with findings that sublethal doses of A β 42 disrupt mitochondrial biosynthesis (Diana and Bono, 2008) and the view that mitochondrial impairment may represent a key event in initial changes leading to EC degeneration (Diana and Bono, 2008; Olajide et al., 2021).

Do we need to combine explanatory elements from each side of the divide?

The hypothesis that infectious agents induce AD has been a controversial issue for decades. However, data accumulated over the past 15 years have led an increasing number of researchers to propose that early A β production is part of an immune response to acute microbial or viral infection of the brain and that this immune response is prone to chronic activation in aging and immunosenescent brains with a compromised brain-blood barrier, increased susceptibility to reinfection and frequent microbial and viral reactivation (Fulop et al., 2018; Butler and Walker, 2021; Wainberg et al., 2021; Li et al., 2021).

We are not in a position to formulate a succinct contrast capturing the wide variety of explanations regarding the early etiology of AD from the other side of the divide, i.e. the multiple hypotheses that do not consider AD as a disease triggered by infectious agents. However, a common foundation for many of these explanations, more or less explicitly stated, is the large body of experimental data showing that numerous tightly networked physiological processes associated with aging converge on silent inflammation, which in turn impact these processes and induce cascade reactions, creating a close link between aging and complex diseases (Franceschi et al., 2018).

The innate immune system is considered the predominant driver of the low-grade chronic and sterile inflammation that characterizes normal aging (Franceschi et al., 2018). Inflammation is intrinsically related to oxidative stress, as ROS can directly or indirectly (through activation of inflammasomes) induce the production of interleukins 1 β , 6 and 18 (IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-18), tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) and chemokines (Vitale et al., 2013). A substantial body of literature supports

the possibility that in the elderly, systemic inflammation caused by infection, chronic diseases, physical and psychological stress, and cell senescence promotes AD (Walker et al., 2019; Spanić et al., 2022). Systemic inflammation may create a proinflammatory environment in the CNS through several routes, inducing reactive, proinflammatory microglia and astrocytic phenotypes capable of promoting A β oligomerization and tau hyperphosphorylation (Walker et al., 2019). Due to their unusually rich innervation by arterioles (Solodkin and Van Hoesen, 1996), ECLII neurons may be particularly vulnerable to bloodborne inflammatory factors (Stranahan and Mattson, 2010). If so, these neurons could be triggered more frequently to produce A β and p-tau than other neurons.

Those favoring the infection hypothesis are confronted with substantial evidence that senescence-driven inflammation is a major causal factor in the early etiology of AD (Walker et al., 2019). Meanwhile, those who deny a role for viral or microbial reinfection or reactivation are confronted with the potent antiviral and antimicrobial properties of A β (Soscia et al., 2010; White et al., 2014; Bourgade et al., 2015; Kumar et al., 2016) and the antiviral properties of p-tau (Eimer et al., 2025). A general observation in the elderly is that physiological responses are induced by agents different from those normally responsible for their activation. If A β and p-tau are indeed part of an ancient immune response, it is fully conceivable that their initial pathological expression in ECLII neurons in early-stage AD is not predominantly driven directly by viral or microbial agents, but by recurrent inflammation events of multifactorial peripheral or CNS origins characteristic of senescent physiology (Franceschi et al., 2018; Furman et al., 2019; Walker et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2023; Mekhora et al., 2024). This simple combination of explanatory elements from both sides opens a portfolio of fresh interpretative possibilities for existing data. It also implies the need for a better understanding of the immune response in which A β and p-tau may be involved and an evolutionary rationale for its existence.

A possible evolutionary rationale for an intraneuronal immune response

The CNS parenchyma is to a substantial degree disconnected from the peripheral immune system in native physiology. It prevents the entry of immune cells through the glial limiting membrane, restrains the migration of resident microglial cells to draining lymph nodes for antigen presentation, and limits lymphatic drainage to small soluble parenchymal antigens (Engelhardt et al., 2017). This unique relationship between the CNS and the immune system has long been known as the 'CNS immune privilege'. The concept has undergone considerable refinement since its inception and

now appears to entail that CNS immune surveillance is maintained by cellular and acellular brain barriers that restrict immune cells and mediator access to specific CNS compartments. This organization allows subsets of immune cells to monitor and respond to the environment within the CNS parenchyma while retaining the ability to react to pathological events of external origin (Proulx and Engelhardt, 2022).

Microglia are resident immune cells of the CNS parenchyma, performing a variety of functions. Pathogen-activated microglia can produce several potentially neurotoxic mediators, such as proteases and proinflammatory cytokines. During inflammation, activated microglia can generate oxidative bursts, releasing high concentrations of ROS to destroy invading pathogens. However, such high levels of ROS threaten neuronal integrity (Joseph and Venero, 2013), suggesting that induction of microglial oxidative bursts might be more tightly regulated than in the case of myeloid phagocytic cells (macrophages and neutrophils) operating in mitotic tissues. Thus, if there has been a net fitness gain associated with avoiding the loss of infected postmitotic neurons compared to simply killing them by autophagy or apoptosis, natural selection may have favored the evolution of an innate intraneuronal immune response designed to serve as a second-line defense against pathogens. This notion is supported by observations that most affected neurons in the AD brain undergo prolonged neurodegeneration and that autophagic or apoptotic cell death does not easily induced even in severely impaired neurons (Ze-Fen Wang et al., 2010). Although many details remain unresolved, it seems fair to conclude that unless it is shown that the antiviral (White et al., 2014; Bourgade et al., 2015) and antimicrobial properties (Soscia et al., 2010; Kumar et al., 2016) of A β and the antiviral properties of p-tau (Eimer et al., 2025) are experimental artifacts, an explanation for the evolution of these functions is warranted.

What can an intraneuronal immune response embody?

Assuming that the observed immunological capabilities of A β and p-tau are products of natural selection and that they are crucial components of a finely tuned regulatory system that may have a somewhat different architecture in different groups of mammals, it follows that understanding how this system operates in native human physiology would probably be instrumental in understanding how it can become dysfunctional in a senescent one. In the following, we address experimental data related to the function of A β and p-tau under native physiological conditions that we believe deserve more attention, and we provide interpretations of these data that deliberately aim to stimulate debate and motivate new directions for experimental work. Figure 1

shows a graphical compilation of how current data can be interpreted in relation to the operation of an intraneuronal immune response in native human physiology and in the legend, with reference to the figure, we briefly recapitulate why we think Re⁺ECLII neurons are particularly vulnerable to dysfunctional activation of this immune response in a senescent physiology characterized by frequent inflammation events.

Is A β 's immune function linked to ROS production?

Cu²⁺ ions bind to A β monomers with very high affinity (Sarell et al., 2009). It is not clear how this binding occurs, but since there are virtually no free copper ions in the cytosol (Rae et al., 1999), the binding process likely involves a chaperone protein. The cytosolic copper chaperone for Cu/Zn superoxide dismutase 1 (Sod1), CCS, is a putative candidate, as it binds to the β -site amyloid precursor protein-cleaving enzyme 1 (BACE1) (Gray et al., 2010), which initiates the APP-processing that leads to A β . Hence, A β monomers can be equipped with a metal ion before being assembled into A β oligomers (A β O) with a length scale of approximately 1 nm (Fulop et al., 2018) by a primary nucleation process (Ashe, 2020). In any case, when an oligomer is bound to Cu²⁺ (or Zn²⁺), it becomes a much more stable construct (Lee et al., 2018). It cannot be excluded that this stabilization is functionally insignificant under native physiological conditions, but we are inclined to believe that the production of stable metal-ion-associated A β oligomer complexes (Me-A β O) is based on a deliberate cellular rationale.

The Me-A β O complex induces the production of free superoxide anions through redox cycling and, subsequently, hydrogen peroxide and hydroxyl radicals (Huang et al., 2019). In the same way that ascorbic acid can act as a source of toxic free radicals in copper-catalyzed reactions (Shen et al., 2021), there are several neuronal molecular candidates, such as thioredoxins, glutaredoxins and peroxiredoxins (Hanschmann et al., 2013), that are possibly capable of donating electrons to Me-A β O complexes to facilitate this production. Since A β O are capable of binding to viruses (Bourgade et al., 2015; Wozniak et al., 2009), as well as microbes (Spitzer et al., 2016), an intriguing possibility is that Me-A β O superoxide anion production serves an immune function. However, it would be an extremely inefficient cellular strategy, hardly favored by natural selection, to induce excessive intracellular ROS production without having a nearby target. Such haphazard production would be avoided if Me-A β O complexes initiate substantial ROS production only when attached to pathogens.

Even contemplating that Me-A β O complexes kill invading pathogens by targeted ROS stress may appear to be an unforgivable long shot, but A β kinetic data point to this possibility. The physiologically relevant redox activity of Cu-A β can be attributed to a coordination sphere between two resting-state complexes (Cas-

sagnes et al., 2013; Girvan et al., 2018). In equilibrium, the coordination sphere capable of fast electron transfer and thus catalyzing ROS production, represents only 0.1% of the Cu-A β species in solution (Cas-sagnes et al., 2013). Cu-A β kinetic data are consistent with a conformational selection mechanism (Girvan et al., 2018), where a ligand can selectively bind to one of several conformations in equilibrium. Conformational selection has been observed for protein-ligand, protein-protein, protein-DNA, protein-RNA, and RNA-ligand interactions underlying signaling, catalysis, gene regulation, and protein aggregation in disease (Girvan et al., 2018). The fact that a macromolecular construct trapped in different conformations when free can be retained in one of the possible conformations when bound (Vogt et al., 2014) makes it conceivable that an initially low-populated reactive intermediate Cu-A β state can become more pronounced when Cu-A β O complexes are associated with a pathogen (Bourgade et al., 2015; Wozniak et al., 2009; Spitzer et al., 2016).

In this context, it is appropriate to mention that the antimicrobial effectiveness of A β against several clinically relevant bacteria has been reported to be on par with, or even superior to that of the canonical human antimicrobial peptide LL-37 (Soscia et al., 2010). The C-terminal helix of this cathelicidin has been shown to be responsible for its antimicrobial and antiviral effects, and the C-terminal tail is important for the formation of tetramers (i.e. oligomers) of cathelicidin peptides in general (Vandamme et al., 2012). Furthermore, when human LL-37 attacks *E. coli* growing aerobically, a single cell fluorescence imaging study (Choi et al., 2017) revealed that LL-37 induces rapid ROS formation (most likely superoxide anion) after entry into the bacterial periplasm, but before permeabilization of the cytoplasmic membrane. That a canonical oligomeric antimicrobial and antiviral (Tripathi et al., 2013) peptide exerts a function that rings similar to the one we have suggested for Me-A β O is at least intriguing.

Does A β 's immune function entail alkalization of endolysosomes?

Most animal virus families, whether enveloped or non-enveloped, exploit the core cellular process of endocytosis to deliver their genomes to the cell interior (Cossart and Helenius, 2014). Through endocytic pathways, incoming viral particles gain access to the acidic environment of endosomal compartments, which frequently provides the conditions required for their penetration into the cytosol. For enveloped viruses, such as herpesviruses, cellular entry depends on the fusion of the viral envelope with the host cell membrane. This membrane fusion is driven by structural rearrangements in viral fusion proteins, typically induced by the low pH within endosomes (Nicola, 2016). As mentioned above, A β appears capable of altering v-ATPase activity to cause endosomal alkalization (Kim et al., 2023). Hence, it seems likely that this A β -driven alkalization mecha-

nism is a deliberate strategy to prevent the spread of a wide class of neurotropic viruses. This alkalization strategy may also prevent the propagation of endocytosed neurotropic bacteria that escape the phagolysosome by producing pore-forming toxins that work optimally at acidic pH (Bonazzi and Cossart, 2006; Geny and Popoff, 2006; Bavdek et al., 2012).

Does A β modulate mitochondrial function?

Epidemiological studies show that exposure to environmental chemicals is a risk factor for AD. Exposing wild-type mice to the herbicide paraquat, which localizes in mitochondria and induces the production of superoxide anion through redox cycling using electrons that constantly leak from the electron transport chain (ETC), has been reported to cause a significantly reduced OXPHOS function through decreased MC-I and MC-IV activities (Chen et al., 2012). Similarly to paraquat, the cancer therapeutics doxorubicin and cisplatin accumulate in mitochondria (Kalyanaraman, 2020; Genc et al., 2014), where they also induce superoxide anion production through redox cycling (Malhi et al., 2012). Both have been found to cause chemotherapy-induced cognitive impairment (or chemobrain) (Ongnok et al., 2020), and long-term administration increases the frequency of mtDNA deletions (Adachi et al., 1993; Genc et al., 2014). Using different antibodies, several studies have reported the presence of A β in mitochondria (Schreiner et al., 2014; Yao et al., 2009; Petersen et al., 2008; Manczak et al., 2006; Caspersen et al., 2005; Lustbader et al., 2004), and it appears likely that A β translocates to mitochondria through the translocase of the outer membrane (TOM) machinery (Petersen et al., 2008). Since translocation of mitochondrial proteins encoded by the nuclear genome is a sequential process that involves threading a precursor protein into the pore of the TOM40 core element (Tucker and Park, 2019), and since the TOM40 pore size is 2-3 nm (Ahting et al., 2001), it does not seem implausible that even a Me-A β O complex can pass through it (Mrdenovic et al., 2019). In any case, we are unaware of any data that argue against the *de novo* assembly of Me-A β O within mitochondria. Because Me-A β O is capable of redox cycling, we think that the possibility that it behaves in mitochondria in a way comparable to paraquat, cisplatin, and doxorubicin should be seriously considered.

Since supraphysiological mitochondrial ROS production can cause mitochondrial impairment, Me-A β O redox cycling in mitochondria seems counterintuitive. If we accept for the moment that Me-A β O complexes do indeed kill pathogens by targeted ROS stress, mitochondrial Me-A β O redox cycling becomes even less plausible, as the total ROS load of neurons would be exacerbated by additional mitochondrial ROS production during a pathogen attack. However, recent data obtained on a wild yeast strain (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, YPS128), which has an intact OXPHOS system similar to that of mammals, can resolve this conundrum

Figure 1. A cartoon of the possible architecture of the immune response that involve A β and tau in cortical neurons. The intraneuronal immune response is anticipated to be highly sophisticated and concerted, and the cartoon represents just a compilation of the components and their interrelations that have been elaborated on in the paper and which have support in the current literature. (A) Following the entry (or anticipated entry through sensing of proinflammatory signals) of a pathogen, increased production of A β causes the formation of p-tau through the reelin-controlled GSK3 β pathway, whereupon p-tau serves to partially disassemble microtubules and thereby hinder pathogen movement along the microtubule network. At least in the case of certain viruses (like HSV-1), the formation of p-tau also serves a direct immune function by attenuating the infectivity of the virus by capsid binding. (B) Alongside bringing about the formation of p-tau, the increased production of A β leads to formation of A β -oligomers that become stabilized by binding to metal ions (Cu-A β O). When Cu-A β O binds to a pathogen it undergoes a conformational shift that enables it to destroy pathogens by targeted production of superoxide anion ($O_2^{\cdot-}$). In addition, A β oligomers hinder the propagation of a wide class of neurotropic viruses and possibly some bacteria by alkalizing endolysosomes through inhibition of the v-ATPase proton pump. (C) Metal-ion-bound A β -oligomers are translocated to mitochondria, where they induce redox cycling by capturing electrons leaking from the ETC to generate intramitochondrial $O_2^{\cdot-}$. This triggers, through retrograde signaling, the deletion of genes coding for key proteins in the ETC in a large number of mtDNAs, which reduces the total ROS load in the cell during operation of the immune response. To maintain the pool of mtDNAs deprived of ETC genes while the cell is working to destroy the invading pathogen, mitophagy is actively repressed by p-tau that has translocated to mitochondria. Upon destruction of the pathogen, A β production drops and the system returns to baseline. The pool of ETC gene deprived mtDNAs is then removed by targeted mitophagy, allowing the remaining wild type mtDNA to repopulate the cell. This immune response can become dysfunctional in a senescent physiology characterized by recurrent sterile inflammation events and increased CNS pathogen exposure and/or reactivation. In each case, the cascade that starts with A β upregulation becomes invoked much more frequently than in native physiology. The reason why Re $^+$ ECLII neurons are especially vulnerable to frequent activation of this response is that the lysosomal aggregation A β_{42}^{reelin} becomes much more pronounced than in cortical neurons expressing low levels of reelin. This leads to enhanced formation of aggregation-prone p-tau fragments on the lysosomal surface. When the soma volume occupancy of lysosome-associated A β_{42}^{reelin} reaches a critical level, it starts to invoke detrimental effects on cellular physiology *per se*. Frequent upregulation of A β can lead to a substantial reduction or even a complete depletion of wild-type mtDNAs, leaving mainly or solely mtDNAs that lack genes critical for ETC function.

(Stenberg et al., 2022). When a cell of this strain is exposed to paraquat, it disables its OXPHOS system by deleting genes coding for key proteins in the ETC. The deletion of mitochondrial DNA has traditionally been attributed to rare accidental events associated with mitochondrial replication or repair of double-strand breaks (Nissanka et al., 2019). Contrary to this perception,

when a YPS128 yeast cell is confronted with paraquat-induced supraphysiological intramitochondrial superoxide anion stress beyond the reach of its normally operating antioxidant defense system, it activates a regulatory system that stops respiration by genetically controlled deletion of OXPHOS genes (Stenberg et al., 2022). The deleted mtDNA segments are unevenly distributed

throughout the mitochondrial genome and are particularly frequent within the region that spans cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COX1) and ribosomal protein variant 1 (VAR1). This mtDNA editing system critically involves the mitochondrially located antioxidant enzyme superoxide dismutase 2 (Sod2) and retrograde/anterograde mitochondrial-nuclear communication and is likely an adaptive trait tuned by natural selection (Stenberg et al., 2022). Thus, in this case, a mitochondrially located redox cyclor inhibits its own activity by turning off the supply of ETC electrons on which it depends. If we assume for the sake of argument that this phenomenon extends to neurons, a cellular rationale for transporting A β to mitochondria may be to reduce general cellular ROS stress, while Me-A β O actively kills pathogens by targeted ROS stress.

While YPS128 yeast cells are exposed to paraquat stress, there is no sign of canonical mitophagy, and mtDNA genomes deprived of key OXPHOS genes are persistently replicated (Stenberg et al., 2022), suggesting that mitophagic signals that could emerge from this deprivation were actively repressed. After release from short-term paraquat stress, the wild-type mtDNA pool is rapidly restored. This implies that replication of mtDNA genomes possessing deletions is actively stopped and/or that the standing pool of these mtDNA genomes is specifically removed by targeted mitophagy. In contrast, sustained exposure to paraquat leads to complete annihilation of the cellular pool of wild-type mitochondrial genomes, causing cells to completely lose their ability to restore respiratory capacity after paraquat release (Stenberg et al., 2022). Under such chronic stress, mtDNA genomes are progressively stripped of DNA until almost the entire 77-kb mtDNA genome (97-99%) is lost and only small segments of less than 1 kb are retained and replicated (Stenberg et al., 2022).

The YPS128 yeast results demonstrate that intramitochondrial superoxide anion stress can cause targeted deletion of mtDNA and active repression of promitophagic signals. Since this is likely an adaptive trait in wild yeast, temporary arrest of mitochondrial ROS production by mtDNA deletion, followed by homeostatic restoration of the pool of intact mitochondrial genomes when relieved from ROS stress, may therefore possibly be a generic eukaryotic adaptation to obviate a more expensive and sometimes counterproductive mitophagic or apoptotic response to supraphysiological ROS stress in a variety of situations. In yeast, this mechanism is demonstrably not designed to handle chronic stress, and there is no evolutionary reason to assume that this would be different in higher eukaryotes. Even if the yeast results do not extend to neurons, we still need to be able to explain why mtDNA deletions increase in AD patients compared to controls (Krishnan et al., 2012; Gerschütz et al., 2013; Hoekstra et al., 2016; Chandrasekaran et al., 1998).

Is p-tau involved in the immune response?

Partially phosphorylated tau contains sequence motifs that promote its binding to tubulin, which regulates the dynamics of microtubules. An individual microtubule in an axon has a stable domain and a labile domain. When tau is experimentally depleted from cultured rat neurons, the mass of the labile microtubule domains drops considerably, indicating that tau is enriched in the labile domain of the microtubule to promote its assembly (Qiang et al., 2018). Since hyperphosphorylation of these motifs mimicks tau depletion, p-tau formation results in loss of microtubule integrity. Because microbes (Yoshida and Sasakawa, 2003) and viruses (Seo and Gammon, 2022) exploit the microtubule network for propagation, tau hyperphosphorylation may thus represent an intraneuronal immune response that limits the intracellular spread of pathogens (Eimer et al., 2025).

P-tau and other forms of tau translocate to mitochondria (Tang et al., 2015; Pérez et al., 2018; Cieri et al., 2018), a phenomenon linked to early AD-related mitochondrial dysfunction. However, the cellular rationale for this remains unclear. If p-tau acts within mitochondria as part of an immune response, there must be an adaptive link between A β , p-tau, and mitochondrial regulation in the context of brain infection.

In yeast cells, mitophagy is actively repressed while mtDNA remains deleted, preserving mitogenesis and preventing loss of genomes carrying adaptive deletions of OXPHOS genes (Stenberg et al., 2022). If A β induces mtDNA deletion as part of a cellular strategy to reduce total ROS stress during pathogen infection, temporary mitophagy repression would serve the same purpose. Therefore, p-tau accumulation in mitochondria can help suppress mitophagic signals when OXPHOS-deficient mtDNA accumulates. Given that p-tau-associated mitophagy dysfunction is a characteristic of AD (Zeng et al., 2022; Pradeepkiran and Reddy, 2020), and considering the high expression of promitophagic Bnip3 in ECLII neurons (Omholt et al., 2024), it is worth asking whether p-tau directly regulates Bnip3.

Tau functions as a signaling hub, interacting with multiple kinases and phosphatases, including the Src family kinases cSrc, Fgr, Fyn, and Lck (Šimić et al., 2016; Mueller et al., 2021). Phosphorylation increases tau's affinity for the tyrosine kinase Fyn (Briner et al., 2020), which also translocates to mitochondria and inhibits AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) (Zhao et al., 2022). Since AMPK activates Unc-51-like kinase 1 (ULK1) by direct phosphorylation (Egan et al., 2011), and ULK1 translocates to dysfunctional mitochondria (Tian et al., 2015) where it promotes mitophagy by stabilizing Bnip3 (Prabhakaran et al., 2007; Poole et al., 2021), it is conceivable that p-tau downregulates mitophagy by modulating the Fyn-AMPK-ULK1-Bnip3 axis.

Importantly, in addition to the above possible immune function of p-tau, p-tau was recently shown to neutralize the infectivity of herpes simplex virus 1 in

neurons by directly binding to viral capsids (Eimer et al., 2025). However, it remains to be decided to what degree p-tau can be considered an antimicrobial protein *per se* (Eimer et al., 2025).

Concluding remarks

The available data and insights from computational modeling support the notion that the dysfunctional operation of an intraneuronal immune response to brain infection established by natural selection may be a prominent culprit behind the development of AD. Based on available data, we are inclined to believe that the main driver of its dysfunction is systemic inflammation rather than chronic reinvasion and reinfection of pathogens. However, there is clearly support for the notion that there may be a notable contribution from the latter mechanism. Regardless of their relative impact, a deeper understanding of the regulatory architecture of this ancient immune response in native physiology would be highly instrumental for understanding the causal chain of events responsible for making ECLII neurons a cradle of AD.

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